

Engineering Iron Dimers at the Atomic Scale for Tunable Biomass Oxidation in Water

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Abstract:

Developing efficient and selective oxidation catalysts is key for advancing sustainable chemical transformations. Herein, we present a durable heterogeneous catalyst featuring single-atom iron dimers anchored on nitrogen-doped graphene acid (Fe-NGA). The catalyst design enables stabilization of redox-flexible Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ centers through coordination with nitrogen and carboxyl groups. During catalysis, these centers generate Fe³⁺–Fe⁴⁺ species, analogous to reactive intermediates in non-heme diiron enzymes, facilitating controlled two-electron oxidation in aqueous media. Spectroscopic analyses, including X-ray absorption and electron paramagnetic resonance, confirm the formation of atomically dispersed, magnetically coupled iron dimers. This cooperative redox behavior is central to the system's high catalytic efficiency. As a demonstration, Fe-NGA catalyzes the oxidation of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) into 2,5-diformylfuran (DFF) with complete HMF conversion, 93% DFF selectivity, and a turnover frequency of 17.3 h⁻¹, ranking among the highest for this transformation. By integrating redox versatility with structural robustness, Fe-NGA establishes a promising strategy for selective oxidation of renewable feedstocks under green conditions.

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